

Economy of Plug-In Charging of Hybrid Car

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Abstract

Charging hybrid car with home electricity saves in Israel 69% of energy cost, 1126 USD per year, in country average. Charging the car with off-peak electricity even increases this saving to 78%, 1261 USD/year. Specific plug-in hybrid car was considered, Honda Clarity 2018.

The saving depends on car parameters, especially the capacity of the battery and its range. Formula was developed in this work for easy calculations of saving in various countries depending on gasoline-to-electricity tariffs ratio, specific to each location. The highest money saving of car's energy cost is in Iceland, Israel, China and Turkey, while in some states in USA plug-in battery charging is not profitable.

Units

This work applies Metric Units. US units' equivalent is shown in some cases in parenthesis.

Fuel consumption metric unit is liter per 100 km, while US unit of the fuel consumption is miles-per-gallon. Lower fuel consumption results in lower value in metric units, but in higher value in US units.

Table 1 - Units conversion applied in this work

US mile	=	1.609344	km
U.S. gallon	=	3.785412	liter

The above conversion table is based on US-DOE units' definitions.

Gasoline Properties

According to DOE [7], the gasoline calorific value is 33.7 kWh/gallon, which is 8.9 kWh/liter.

Plug-In Hybrid Car

The difference between the hybrid car and plug-in hybrid car is in possibility of charging the car's battery when parking with engine switched off using electric cable from home, office or charging station.

The difference between plug-in hybrid car and electric car is in gasoline engine of plug-in hybrid car, while electric car has no gasoline engine. Electric car must have much bigger battery than the plug-in hybrid car to have reasonable range of few hundreds kilometers, resulting in bigger weight, car cost, battery replacement cost and longer battery charging time.

Car Specifications

The car analyzed in this work is Honda Clarity 2018 [1]. The car type is Plug-In Hybrid car.

From publication [2]: *"it has a 75-km range on battery power. The Clarity can run solely on electric power up until 160 km/h – you can basically boot it and it will stay in electric. Engine: 1.5-litre Atkinson cycle four-cylinder engine/17 kWh electric battery pack. Transmission/drive: Electronic/front-wheel. Fuel economy (litres/100 km, city/highway): 5.6"*.

The publication [1] claims that this car is "class-leading" 47 mile all-electric range rating.

The battery is Li-Ion type, 17 kWh capacity.

Battery plug-in charging time is 2.5 hours with 220-240V, 30A, and 12 hours with 120V.

According to publication [1] the car's range is 47 miles. This is equivalent to 76 km.

However publication [2] indicates 75 km range, equivalent to 46.6 miles.

For the purpose of conservativeness, the range applied in this work will be 75 km.

Battery Efficiency

Publication [3] claims that Li-Ion battery charging efficiency is 99% and the discharge loss is "small". Base on this source of information the battery energy efficiency will be regarded in this work as 98%.

Electric Motor Efficiency

Electric motor efficiency applied in this work is 98%.

Table 2 - Electric drive efficiency

Battery	98%
Motor	98%
Σ	96.04%

Electricity Specific Consumption

Table 3 - Electricity specific consumption [1]

Parameter	Value	Unit	Reference
Battery capacity	17	kWh	[1]
Battery-only range	75	km	[2]
Battery charging efficiency	99%		[3]
Electricity specific consumption	0.229	kWh/km	
Electricity specific consumption	22.9	kWh/100km	

Based on publication [1] (Honda official site) the electricity specific consumption is 0.227 kWh/km. Considering 1% electricity loss when charging the battery, the grid electricity specific consumption is 0.229 kWh/km

The following table is based on publication [7].

Table 4 - Electricity specific consumption [7]

Parameter	Value	Unit	Reference
Electric drive specific consumption	31	kWh/100mile	[7]
Electric drive specific consumption	19.263	kWh/100km	
Electric drive specific consumption	0.193	kWh/km	

Based on publication [7] (US-DOE official site) the electricity specific consumption is 0.193 kWh/km, however more conservative result was selected for further analysis, which is 0.229 kWh/km.

Gasoline Engine Efficiency

Table 5 - Gasoline Engine Efficiency

Parameter	Value	Unit	Reference
Electric	110	MPG	[7]
Gasoline	42	MPG	[7]
Electric/Gasoline	2.619		
Electric drive efficiency	96%		
Gasoline engine efficiency	37%		

The result of the above calculation is gasoline engine efficiency of 37%.

This is very high efficiency comparing to the current (year 2018) common opinion. According to publications [5] and [6] most gasoline combustion engines in typical US driving conditions average around 20 percent thermal efficiency, while 38% efficiency of Toyota engine is regarded as unusual extreme.

From publication [1]: "Gasoline-Only (MPG, City/Highway/Combined) 44 / 40 / 42". To convert MPG to l/100km online converter [4] was applied.

Table 6 - Gasoline only fuel specific consumption

	MPG	L/100km
City	44	5.35
Highway	40	5.88
Combined	42	5.60

The above table based on Honda official information seems to be not correct as usually the city fuel consumption is higher than highway. However the combined fuel consumption of 5.60 L/100km is in line with other publications [2] and [7] and this value will be applied for further analysis.

Energy Tariffs in Israel

Gasoline tariff is according to actual receipt from self service gas station from January 2018. In Israel the gasoline tariffs are constant in the same month. The USD average exchange rate was in January 2018 - 3.4232 ILS/USD. This results if gasoline tariff in Israel 1.8082 USD/liter.

Table 7 - Gasoline tariff in Israel, self service

Parameter	Value	Unit	Source
Fuel tariff	6.19	ILS/liter	actual receipt
Exchange rate	3.4232	ILS/USD	Bank of Israel
Fuel tariff	1.8082	USD/liter	

Table 8 - Electricity residential tariffs 2018 [9]

Parameter	Value	Unit	Source
Residential tariff	0.4619	ILS/kWh	[9]
Exchange rate	3.4232	ILS/USD	Bank of Israel
Residential tariff	0.1349	USD/kWh	

Table 9 - Electricity low Voltage off-peak tariffs 2018, weighted average [9]

	Winter	Spring/Fall	Summer	Year
ILS/kWh	0.3615	0.3252	0.3357	0.3360
months/y	3	7	2	

Table 10 - Electricity low Voltage off-peak tariffs 2018, weighted average

Parameter	Value	Unit	Source
Off-peak ave tariff	0.3360	ILS/kWh	[9]
Exchange rate	3.4232	ILS/USD	Bank of Israel
Off-peak ave tariff	0.0982	USD/kWh	

Cost of Driving 100 km

Table 11 - Cost of driving 100 km

Gasoline-only	10.13	USD/100km
Battery-only residential tariff	3.09	USD/100km
Battery-only off-peak tariffs	2.25	USD/100km

Yearly Saving – Israel

The average use of private car applied in this work is 16,000 km per.

Table 12 - Yearly saving by using battery-only drive

Use of car	16,000	km/y
Gasoline only	1,620	USD/y
Battery-only residential tariff	494	USD/y
Saving	1,126	USD/y
Saving	69%	
Battery-only off-peak tariffs	360	USD/y
Saving	1,261	USD/y
Saving	78%	

Economic Evaluation

Table 13 - Inputs to economic evaluation

Economic lifetime	10	Years
Rate of interest	3.50%	%/y
Use of car	16,000	km/y
Yearly saving	1,126	USD/y

Table 14 - Economic Evaluation

CRF	0.1202	
PV	9,364	USD
Max additional investment	9,364	USD
ROI (0%)	8.3	years

Maximum justified cost increase comparing to not plug-in car is 9,364 USD for Israeli conditions.

Sensitivity Analysis - Israel

Table 15 - Break-even gasoline tariff

Current fuel cost	1.8082	USD/liter
Gasoline only	10.13	USD/100km
Battery only residential tariff	3.09	USD/100km
Ratio	0.3051	
Break-even gasoline cost	0.5517	USD/liter
Break-even gasoline cost	2.0883	USD/gallon

There will be no economic benefit for battery plug-in charging if the gasoline tariff is 0.5517 USD/liter (2.0883 USD/gallon) or less, considering current electricity tariff of 0.1349 USD/kWh (Israel 2018).

Yearly Saving – Virginia

According to DOE-EIA [11] residential electricity tariffs in November 2017 were as follows:

- Virginia: 11.67 USD/kWh
- New York: 17.81 USD/kWh
- Connecticut: 20.70 USD/kWh

These very high electricity tariffs combined with very low gasoline tariffs make the plug-in charge not profitable.

Virginia was selected for further analysis, as most suitable for the use of plug-in charge.

According to [8] the energy tariffs in Virginia are as follows:

- Regular Gasoline \$ 2.61 per gallon
- Electricity Home: \$ 0.10 per kWh

According to the specific fuel centers in Virginia [10], the gasoline cost in Virginia is as follows:

- fuel center 1: US\$2.36/Standard
- fuel center 2: US\$2.39/Standard

Table 16 - Gasoline tariffs in Virginia

DOE	2.61	USD/gallon	[8]
Kroger 1	2.36	USD/gallon	[10]
Kroger 2	2.39	USD/gallon	[10]
lowest	2.36	USD/gallon	

The most conservative value will be applied, which is 2.36 USD/gallon.

According to source [12] residential electricity tariffs in Virginia average 11.08¢/kWh, 6.73% less than the US national average residential rate of 11.88¢/kWh. According to the electric utility [13], residential customers of Appalachian Power in Virginia pay approximately 11.7 cents per kilowatt-hour (kWh) for electricity.

Table 17 - Electricity tariffs in Virginia

Source	USD/kWh
[8]	0.1000
[11]	0.1167
[12]	0.1108
[13]	0.1170
highest	0.1170

The most conservative value will be applied, which is 0.1170 USD/kWh. According to [14] vehicle miles per driver in Virginia are 15,464 miles/y.

Table 18 - Yearly saving – Virginia

Car miles	15,464	miles/y
Car km	24,887	km/y
Gasoline L/100 km	5.60	L/100 km
Electricity specific consumption	22.9	kWh/100km
Gasoline tariff	2.36	USD/gallon
Gasoline tariff	0.62	USD/liter
Gasoline per year	1,394	liter/y
Gasoline cost	869	USD/y
Electricity tariff	0.1170	USD/kWh
Electricity per year	5,698	kWh/y
Electricity cost	667	USD/y
Saving	202	USD/y
Saving	23%	

Comparison of saving in Israel and Virginia

Table 19 - Comparison of saving in Israel and Virginia

Parameter	Unit	Israel	Virginia	Δ
Use of car	km/y	16,000	24,887	56%
Gasoline tariff	USD/liter	1.81	0.62	-66%
Gasoline cost	USD/y	1,620	869	-46%
Electricity tariff	USD/kWh	0.1349	0.1170	-13%
Electricity cost	USD/y	494	667	35%
Saving	USD/y	1,126	202	-82%
Saving	%	69%	23%	-67%

The above table shows that plug-in charging of hybrid car is much more profitable in Israel than in Virginia. It may be assumed that in other US states with higher electricity tariffs, like NY, MA and CT, plug-in charging is not profitable at all.

Formula for Saving Calculations

Formula 1 - Gasoline-only fuel cost

$$\text{Gas\$} = \text{Ucar} * \text{GasKm} * \text{GasLit} / 100$$

Gas\$	gasoline-only fuel cost [USD/year]
Ucar	use of car [km/year]
GasKm	gasoline specific consumption [liters/100km]
GasLit	gasoline tariff [USD/liter]

Formula 2 - Battery-only electricity cost

$$\text{EL\$} = \text{Ucar} * \text{ELkm} * \text{ELkWh}$$

EL\$	battery-only electricity cost [USD/year]
Ucar	use of car [km/year]
ELkm	electricity specific consumption [kWh/km]
ELkWh	electricity tariff [USD/kWh]

Formula 3 - Electricity specific consumption

$$\text{ELkm} = \text{BaCap} / (\text{ELrange} * \text{BaEff})$$

BaCap	battery capacity [kWh]
ELrange	range driving on battery only [km]
BaEff	battery charging efficiency = 99%

Formula 4 - Battery-only electricity cost

$$\text{EL\$} = \text{Ucar} * \text{BaCap} * \text{ELkWh} / (\text{ELrange} * \text{BaEff})$$

Formula 5 - Saving in USD

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Save\$} &= \text{Gas\$} - \text{EL\$} = \\
 &= \text{Ucar} * \text{GasKm} * \text{GasLit} / 100 - \text{Ucar} * \text{BaCap} * \text{ELkWh} / (\text{ELrange} * \text{BaEff}) = \\
 &= \text{Ucar} * (\text{GasKm} * \text{GasLit} / 100 - \text{BaCap} * \text{ELkWh} / (\text{ELrange} * \text{BaEff}))
 \end{aligned}$$

Save\$ saving [USD/y]
 Gas\$ gasoline-only fuel cost [USD/year]
 EL\$ battery-only electricity cost [USD/year]

Formula 6 - Saving in %

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Save\%} &= 1 - \text{EL\$} / \text{Gas\$} = \\
 &= 1 - [\text{Ucar} * \text{BaCap} * \text{ELkWh} / (\text{ELrange} * \text{BaEff})] / [\text{Ucar} * \text{GasKm} * \text{GasLit} / 100] = \\
 &= 1 - 100 * \text{BaCap} * \text{ELkWh} / (\text{ELrange} * \text{BaEff} * \text{GasKm} * \text{GasLit}) = \\
 &= 1 - [\text{ELkWh} / \text{GasLit}] * [100 * \text{BaCap} / (\text{ELrange} * \text{BaEff} * \text{GasKm})]
 \end{aligned}$$

Save% saving [%]
 EL\$ battery-only electricity cost [USD/year]
 Gas\$ gasoline-only fuel cost [USD/year]

There are 2 groups of parameters in the above formula:

- ELkWh and GasLit are related to energy tariffs depending on country. This group of parameters shall be determined as Gasoline-to-Electricity Tariffs Ratio - GETrat.
- BaCap, ELrange, BaEff, GasKm are related to car specification and remain constant between countries. This group of parameters shall be determined as Car Constant – CarK.

Formula 7 - Gasoline-to-Electricity Tariffs Ratio (GETrat)

$$\text{GETrat} = \text{GasLit} / \text{ELkWh}$$

Formula 8 - Car Constant (CarK)

$$\mathbf{CarK = 100 * BaCap / (ELrange * BaEff * GasKm)}$$

Formula 9 - Application of GETrat and CarK

$$\mathbf{Save\% = 1 - CarK / GETrat}$$

GETrat Gasoline-to-Electricity Tariffs Ratio [kWh/liter]
CarK Car Constant [kWh/liter]

To make the calculations easier, the cars' manufacturers may publish the CarK specific for each model and ministries of energy may publish the GETrat for each location.

GETrat for Israel

Formula 7:

$$\mathbf{GETrat = GasLit / ELkWh}$$

Table 20 - GETrat for Israel

Parameter	ID	Value	Unit
Electricity tariff	ELkWh	0.1349	USD/kWh
Gasoline tariff	GasLit	1.8082	USD/liter
Gasoline-to-Electricity Tariffs Ratio	GETrat	13.4	kWh/liter

CarK for Honda Clarity 2018

CarK is calculated applying Formula 8.

Formula 8:

$$\text{CarK} = 100 * \text{BaCap} / (\text{ELrange} * \text{BaEff} * \text{GasKm})$$

Table 21 - CarK for Honda Clarity 2018

Parameter	ID	Value	Unit
Battery capacity	BaCap	17	kWh
Range driving on battery only	ELrange	75	km
Battery charging efficiency	BaEff	99%	
Gasoline specific consumption	GasKm	5.60	liters/100km
Car Constant	CarK	4.089	kWh/liter

Validation of the Formulas

Formula 5:

$$\text{Save\$} = \text{Ucar} * (\text{GasKm} * \text{GasLit} / 100 - \text{BaCap} * \text{ELkWh} / (\text{ELrange} * \text{BaEff}))$$

Table 22 - Validation of Formula 5 for Israel

Parameter	ID	Value	Unit
Use of car	Ucar	16,000	km/y
Gasoline specific consumption	GasKm	5.60	liters/100km
Gasoline tariff	GasLit	1.81	USD/liter
Battery capacity	BaCap	17	kWh
Electricity tariff	ELkWh	0.13	USD/kWh
Range driving on battery only	ELrange	75	km
Battery charging efficiency	BaEff	0.99	
Saving	Save\$	1,126	USD/y
Previous calculation result		1,126	USD/y
Validation OK?		TRUE	

Formula 9:

$$\text{Save\%} = 1 - \text{CarK} / \text{GETrat}$$

Table 23 - Validation of Formula 9

Parameter	ID	Value	Unit
Gasoline-to-Electricity Tariffs Ratio	GETrat	13.40	kWh/liter
Car Constant	CarK	4.089	kWh/liter
Saving	Save%	69%	
Previous calculation result		69%	
Validation OK?		TRUE	

Critical GETrat

Critical GETrat is the GETrat for which $\text{Save\%} = 0$.

Formula 9:

$$\text{Save\%} = 1 - \text{CarK} / \text{GETrat}$$

Formula 10 - Critical GETrat

$$\text{Save\%} = 1 - \text{CarK} / \text{GETrat} = 0$$

$$1 = \text{CarK} / \text{GETrat}$$

$$\mathbf{\text{GETratCR} = \text{CarK}}$$

For Honda Clarity 2018 the GETratCR is 4.089 kWh/liter.

Examples of Application of GETrat Parameter

Internet site Global Petrol Prices [15] includes gasoline updated prices in many countries. The data may be displayed in USD/liter.

The highest gasoline tariffs are in Iceland 2.09 USD/L.

Site [16] includes electricity tariffs in some countries for year 2017 in USD/kWh.

The highest electricity tariffs are in Germany 0.33 USD/kWh.

Table 24 - Examples of application of GETrat parameter for Honda Clarity 2018

	Gasoline	Electricity	GETrat	Save%	Source
	USD/liter	USD/kWh			
Australia Min	1.11	0.11	10.09	59%	15, 17
Australia Ave	1.11	0.19	6.00	32%	15, 17
Australia Max	1.11	0.26	4.27	4%	15, 17
Canada	1.07	0.08	13.38	69%	15, 16
Canada Min	1.07	0.08	13.38	69%	15, 17
Canada Ave	1.07	0.12	8.92	54%	15, 17
Canada Max	1.07	0.16	6.69	39%	15, 17
China	1.17	0.09	13.00	69%	15, 16
China Min	1.17	0.05	23.40	83%	15, 17
China Ave	1.17	0.10	12.32	67%	15, 17
China Max	1.17	0.14	8.36	51%	15, 17
France	1.77	0.20	8.85	54%	15, 16
France	1.77	0.19	9.20	56%	15, 17
Germany	1.66	0.33	5.03	19%	15, 16
Germany	1.66	0.34	4.92	17%	15, 17
Iceland	2.09	0.15	14.41	72%	15, 17
Israel	1.81	0.13	13.40	69%	this work
Israel	1.87	0.15	12.18	66%	15, 17
New Zealand	1.55	0.19	8.09	49%	15, 17
Russia	0.73	0.09	8.11	50%	15, 17
Spain	1.49	0.26	5.73	29%	15, 16
Spain	1.49	0.20	7.56	46%	15, 17
Turkey	1.46	0.11	13.04	69%	15, 17
UK	1.67	0.24	6.96	41%	15, 16
UK	1.67	0.25	6.68	39%	15, 17
UK	1.67	0.19	9.01	55%	15, 18
USA-VA	0.62	0.12	5.33	23%	this work
USA	0.75	0.21	3.57	No Profit	15, 16
USA	0.75	0.13	5.91	31%	15, 17
Ave	1.34	0.17	8.00	49%	this table
World Ave	1.52	0.17	9.10	55%	15
Max				83%	

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